

Reaction of Chloral with Ferric Chloride

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Hydrolysis of chloral or chloral hydrate started above 63°C in the presence of ferric chloride, giving very high yields of carbon monoxide and hydrogen chloride and a small amount of a crystalline cyclic trimer of chloral, m.p., 155-56°C.

CARBON tetrachloride and trichloromethyl compounds were found to undergo hydrolysis in the presence of hydrated ferric chloride¹. Carbon tetrachloride gave high yield of phosgene according to the following reaction

1,1,1-trichloroethane ($\text{Cl}_3\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$) and benzotrichloride ($\text{Cl}_3\text{C}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) under similar condition respectively gave considerable quantity of acetic acid and benzoic acid but chloroform, that for similar reason was expected to give formic acid, acted only as a solvent. It thus would seem that the groups attached to trichloromethyl considerably influence the course of the reaction. The present investigation was carried out to study the effect of carbonyl group attached to trichloromethyl part and chloral ($\text{Cl}_3\text{C}-\text{CHO}$) was selected for the purpose.

Chloral and water or chloral hydrate did not undergo any reaction in the presence of anh. ferric chloride with or without solvent below 63°C but above this temperature afforded CO and HCl almost quantitatively according to the following reaction

Besides, a silky crystalline product, m.p. 155-56°C, was isolated (yield, 4.40%). Elemental analysis indicated that it had empirical formula, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_9$, and the infrared analysis showed the absence of carbonyl group and the presence of C-O-C link (1090 cm^{-1}) and polychlorinated bond (785 cm^{-1}). Other conventional analytical tests also indicated it to be a trimer of chloral, ($\text{Cl}_3\text{C}-\text{CHO}$)₃.

Hill² regarded the hydrolytic reaction of trichloromethyl compounds to proceed through a reactive trichloromethyl complex with metal halides such as $\text{Cl}_3\text{C}^+.\text{Fe}_2\text{Cl}_7^-$; the trichloromethyl cation then undergoing a nucleophilic attack by water to give phosgene and hydrogen chloride in the case of carbon tetrachloride, for example. The formation of carbon monoxide and hydrogen chloride from chloral appeared to support such a view. Nucleophilic water

molecule was expected to attack the more positive carbonium ion, $\text{Cl}_3\text{C}^+ \rightarrow \overset{\text{O}}{\parallel} \text{C}^+ \text{CH Fe}_2\text{Cl}_7^-$, yielding finally CO and HCl, according to the following reaction

Experimental

Hydrolysis of chloral hydrate: (A) *Detection of gaseous products:* A mixture of chloral hydrate (8.30 g, 0.05 mole) and anhydrous ferric chloride (8.24 g, 0.05 mole) was warmed on a water bath in a flask fitted with outlet leading first into etheral solution of aniline, then into water and finally into freshly prepared AgNO_3 solution. The mixture started melting at 55°C and gave out gas at 63°C, and it was heated for 5 hr at 65°C till evolution of bubbles ceased. The mixture in the flask turned to an almost dried mass. The etheral solution of aniline gave after about 16 hr feather-like crystals which were separated, recrystallised twice from ether. The product, m.p. 197-198°C, was identified as aniline hydrochloride. Water gave acid test to litmus, produced vigorous effervescence with aq. NaHCO_3 , and gave curdy white ppt. with AgNO_3 soluble in NH_4OH . These showed the presence of HCl. At the end of 4 hr black mirror appeared on the walls of the conical flask that contained AgNO_3 solution, indicating the formation of CO.

(B) *Examination of the residue* : The black mass left at the end of the reaction was extracted with ether. The solvent was slowly evaporated and the semi-crystalline mass was dissolved in small portions in CCl_4 and solvent removed. The light brownish product on recrystallisation from 60% ethanol afforded white silky crystals, m.p. $155-56^\circ\text{C}$, soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in water. It did not decolorise bromine in carbon tetrachloride, potassium permanganate solution and did not react with dimedone, 2,4-DNP and semicarbazide. ν_{max} 1090 cm^{-1} (-C-O-C-) and 785 cm^{-1} (polychlorinated link). (Found : C, 17.07; H, 0.88; Cl, 72.05. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_9$ requires C, 16.27; H, 0.68; Cl, 72.20).

When chloral (0.1 mole) itself was reacted with ferric chloride (0.1 mole) to which was added calculated amount of water (0.1 mole) drop-wise at 65°C , the reaction proceeded at faster rate than the hydrated variety as judged from the rate of evolution of bubbles and the period of completion of the reaction (4 hr). The proportion of the trimer, m.p. $155-156^\circ\text{C}$, was also almost the same.

Reference

1. M. E. HILL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1115.